

Association of Sound movements in space to Takete and Maluma

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes an experiment that has been performed to verify if the well known association between the words “takete” and “maluma” and the images of two shapes (one jagged and one rounded) could be replicated using two sound movements in space instead of the visual shapes. In this case the association is not cross-modal since both the stimuli are in the auditory domain, but the connection between words and sound movements is not trivial. A significant preference (twelve out of thirteen subjects) associated “takete” with the jagged sound movement and “maluma” with the round one. Colored noise was used as stimulus. The qualitative answers of the subjects suggest also a possible common expressive intention that could be conveyed by the two words/sound movements: an aggressive attitude to “takete” and a more calm and feminine one to “maluma”.

1. INTRODUCTION

Several experiments have been performed since 1929, when Wolfgang Köler found out that there is a general tendency to associate rounded shapes with words containing the vowel “o” and “u” while more jagged shapes with words containing the vowels “e” or “i” [1, 2]. Köler showed for the first time that there is a privileged association between shapes attributes and auditory dimensions. While he was mostly looking into the “angular” dimension of this correspondence, other studies proved it with respect, for instance, to size [3] or aspect ratio [4]. This cross-modal association is present across cultures, and from an early age [5]. The above mentioned effect can be included in the so called *arbitrary-looking cross-modal matchings* [6] that includes cross-modal associations between words and tastes [7], shapes and flavours [8], shapes and smells [9] and also words and kinaesthetic feedback [10]. In this paper we investigate the association between words and sound movement in space. Both the stimuli are auditory one, but the association is not trivial at all. Sound movement into space is a sound parameter that can not easily be associated with words. The idea of this investigation is that sound move-

ment per se can convey expressive intentions as many other sound parameters [11] and that at the same time the same expressive intentions can be conveyed by the sounds of the words Takete and Maluma. So the association is highly correlated to the conveyed expressive content.

Figure 1. Takete and Maluma as used in Köler’s experiment.

2. METHOD

The experiment has been carried out in the Multisensory Experience Lab of the Sound and Music Computing group of Aalborg University in Copenhagen, see fig. 2.

Figure 2. The Multisensory Experience lab at Aalborg University in Copenhagen

2.1 Participants

A total of 13 subjects performed both tests. The subjects’ average age was 24.4, the youngest subject being 19 years old while the oldest was 34. There were a total of 11 male and 2 female participants, and 5 among them had some musical background and/or were studying an instrument. Each test lasted around 3 minutes. Participants were rewarded with a movie ticket.

which does not impact significantly on the perception of the source itself.

Thus, it may come as a surprise to find that when the position of the source is dynamic, that is when the sound source moves with respect to the listener, the quality of the movement is easily associated to the quality of words, replicating quite closely the results of a famous gestalt experiment such as the “takete/maluma” one.

On the other hand, one could say that music composers have understood, albeit intuitively perhaps, the potential expressivity of sound moving through space since many years now. If we do not want to trace back the expressive potential of sound localisation to the “cori bantenti” of the Gabrieli brothers in XVI century, we are well aware that in the most important contemporary music compositions of the past fifty years movement of sound in space has constituted a major expressive element. Boulez’ *Répons*, the *Prometeo* by Nono, Stockhausen’s *Kontakte* and *Oktophonie* and Berio’s *Ofanim* are but a few of the most prominent examples of musical works which feature sound movement in space as an essential expressive element. These (and other) compositions led to early investigation on the expressive potential of sound movement in space [11, 12].

This experiment consolidates the idea that indeed, there is a connection between sound movement in space and expression, and that this connection is quite reliable and robust (at least for clearly defined patterns such as those used for “takete” and “maluma”).

4. CONCLUSION

An exploration of the association between sound movement in space and the words “takete” and “maluma” was carried out through a specific experiment involving two contrasting sound movement trajectories. The results confirm the pattern presented in the original experiment by Köler: “takete” is associated with the jagged trajectory, while “maluma” is associated with the rounded one. The use of sound movement instead of the visual feedback opens the investigation to further questions: do subjects associate the sound movement trajectory to the corresponding image? is it the spatial or the temporal analogy guiding the performance of the subject? Further research should be conducted on the same topic, providing for instance the two words in print instead of verbal utterances and/or testing with different trajectory pairs.

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